

RI-VIS D2.3 Report on the dissemination for white papers

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable summarises the activities of task 2.4 which builds on tasks 2.1 – 2.3 (mapping RIs and their services (task 2.1), identifying and analysing gaps in communication and stakeholder engagements (task 2.2) and providing recommendations on future collaboration (2.3)). The results of the analyses and the recommendations have been provided as three White Papers taking into account regional characteristics. Task 2.4 aimed at enabling decision makers both on policy and research infrastructure management levels to make optimal use of the analyses and recommendations to strengthen international collaboration. To that end, multiple dissemination activities have been performed using RI-VIS channels and well-established channels outside RI-VIS. Next to describing these dissemination activities in detail, this deliverable also provides information on how the White Papers will be made available and sustained beyond the RI-VIS project lifetime.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

The dissemination of the three regional White Paper recommendations towards cooperation between European research infrastructures and those in three world regions (Africa [1], Latin America [2] and Australia [3]) will ensure that decision makers on both policy and research infrastructure management levels will be enabled to make optimal use of these recommendations provided by tasks 2.2 and 2.3 towards strengthening international collaborations. To this end, taking into account COVID-19-related limitations, outreach activities have been organized by RI-VIS and WP2, (e.g. WP3 conferences as well as those of research infrastructure clusters to further support European infrastructures and their counterparts) targeting European and international research infrastructures, policymakers and stakeholders providing a platform to share the recommendations and discuss their potential implications.

Task 2.4 made use of synergies with existing communication and dissemination channels to reach out to these target groups. Those included channels within the RI-VIS project and its single

consortium partners, but also well-established channels in the research infrastructure landscape beyond RI-VIS.

While mainly aiming to disseminate the three White Papers provided by WP2, task 2.4 synergistically supported the dissemination of RI-VIS products provided by other WPs. In concrete terms, when targeting specific stakeholders with the White Papers it added further RI-VIS products which promised additional benefits to these stakeholders.

Thus, task 2.4 also worked synergistically and complemented the activities of:

- Task 1.4: Project website for information dissemination and project documentation;
- Task 2.1: Mapping services to new target communities;
- Task 2.2: Analyse the research infrastructure landscape;
- Task 2.3: Provide guidelines and advice for targeting and enabling new partnerships;
- Task 3.1: Identification of a champion in each international target;
- Task 3.2: Develop an outreach strategy for each region with the RIs and the champions;
- Task 3.3: Organize 3 thematic workshops and partnering events in three different regions;
- Task 3.4: Publicity of the outreach events by website, social media, publication;
- Task 4.2: Provide information for common communication platforms across all thematic RI groups;
- Task 4.4: Provide guidelines to promote the development of new cooperative relationships;
- Task 5.2: Tailoring Communication Approaches;
- Task 5.3: Increase international visibility and usage of research infrastructures;

Description of work

In concrete terms, this task disseminated the White Papers and further RI-VIS products via the following RI-VIS channels:

- RI-VIS digital & social media activities, including the RI-VIS website [4], newsletter and twitter account. The RI-VIS Twitter account has 871 followers as of November 2021. However by cooperating with research infrastructure accounts and engaging with followers, RI-VIS tweets promoting the White Papers have gained more than 30,000 impressions (views) on Twitter.
- RI-VIS communicator slack channel [5]: RI-VIS has established a slack channel, integrating communication experts from the whole RI community (also beyond RI-VIS partnership), bringing together the knowledge and expertise of more than 350 communication experts multipliers.
- RI-VIS International Symposia of Research Infrastructures: The White Papers have been made available via Zenodo and the conference platform to all participants of the events in advance of the symposia, with more than 1,800 downloads. They have also been provided as background documents in specific panel discussions during the conferences, bringing together high-level experts discussing on the current state and opportunities for the future of collaboration. In total, the White Papers were brought forwards to more than 500 RI experts covering both policy makers and RI managers in four world regions (Latin America, Africa, Australia, Europe)

- RI-VIS consortium partners: The White Papers have been available to all 13 partners of the RI-VIS project and their international counterparts, as a means of support to be used for their own needs in developing their stakeholder engagement strategies and activities across regions.

Task 2.4 further made use of the following channels beyond RI-VIS:

- ICRI, the International Conference on Research Infrastructures, engages policy experts, facility managers, leading researchers and a variety of other stakeholders to discuss challenges and emerging trends for research infrastructures around the world. This core event for the global RI landscape took recently place virtually in June 2021 and brought together nearly 700 participants from all continents [6]. Various RI-VIS consortium partners participated in the exhibition of the event via virtual booths, presenting next to their single RIs also RI-VIS White Papers and further products.
- EU-LAC ResInfra [7] is a Horizon 2020 funded EU project and aims to increase bi-regional collaboration in the area of research infrastructures between Europe and Latino America. The White Paper will be used within the discussions of sustainability of the project. It will be also discussed by the four pilot research infrastructures within the implementation work package of the project.
- European Life Science RIs [8] jointly provide a catalogue of services to their user communities, complemented by joint dissemination activities. The White Papers have been disseminated via these established channels, reaching about 300 experts in the life science domains.
- The ERIC Forum Implementation Project [9] is a Horizon2020 project bringing together 20 established European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and 3 ERICs in preparation across all research domains to strengthen their coordination and enhance collaborations between the partners through targeted activities addressing their needs in close collaboration with European stakeholders. WP2 has provided the ERIC Forum with the White Papers for dissemination through their channels thus contributing to increase awareness regarding the challenges and recommendations towards establishing sustainable partnerships with RIs in the three different world regions.
- BEERI [10] is the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures, strategically supporting the environmental research infrastructure community [11] in Europe. It brings together 26 RIs that are studying different aspects of the Earth system. Fourteen Research Infrastructures are listed on the latest edition of the ESFRI Roadmap, which means they are the most advanced ones in their operations and the services they offer. Task 2.4 has brought the White Papers and further RI-VIS products into the regular BEERI meetings in order to encourage and support their application in the further strategic development of the community and its single RIs.
- RItrain Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures [12]: RItrain, the Research Infrastructure Training Programme, is an EU-funded Horizon 2020 project aimed at improving and professionalizing the training of managerial and leadership staff in research infrastructures (RIs). Next to staff exchange programmes and webinars, it provides an Executive Master Programme delivered by the University of Milano Bicocca, tailored for busy executives and organising its 60 ECTS into a mixture of face-to-face and online activities held by international faculty and top managers from RIs. Task 2.4 has been contributing to the “Raising Awareness” module by providing a 3-hour session on communication, including

information and discussion on RI-VIS products, targeting 25 RI decision makers at directorship level.

- CatRIS (Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services) [13] is a EU funded H2020 project, aiming at providing an open, trusted and user-friendly portal to a harmonised and aggregated catalogue of services and resources provided by RIs. CatRIS was approached by Task 2.4 and disseminated the white papers within its user-community via its social media channels.
- ENRIITC [14], a Horizon 2020 funded EU-project, is the European Network of Research Infrastructures and Industry for Collaboration, bringing together eleven RI project partners and further 62 RI associated partners. It supports the establishment of strategic- cross-border partnerships between industry and RIs by (1) establishing a sustainable European network of Industry Liaison and Contact Officers (2) develop and refine strategies and best practices to foster these collaborations, and (3) raise awareness among industry for collaboration opportunities with RIs. Next to providing the White Papers to project coordination, RI-VIS will hold a specific session during the upcoming 5th season of the #ENRIITCyourCoffee webinar series. In this well-established format, people come together online for 30 minutes each week to learn, discuss, collaborate and stay connected.

Conclusion/Next steps

The three White Papers and further major RI-VIS products have been disseminated directly to a wide range of decision-makers in politics and RI management, but also potential multipliers that reach decision makers that could not be targeted directly by RI-VIS. Many of these decision makers hold long-term roles in their host organisations, ensuring that the recommendations provided by this task will impact RI cooperation beyond the lifetime of the RI-VIS project. In addition, this task adopted activities in line with the RI-VIS sustainability planning to complement this effect, i.e. in concrete terms:

- The White Papers and all further products have been made available via the open-access repository Zenodo, ensuring that the community can access them beyond the RI-VIS lifetime.
- The website ri-vis.eu and the respective domain presenting among others the White Papers will be maintained at least for 5 further years by Instruct-ERIC.
- With some of the main contributors to the White Papers being integrated in the RI-VIS communicator slack channel, questions and feedback on the white papers can be processed beyond the RI-VIS lifetime.

References

- [1] S. Fahrner, L. Vincenz-Donnelly, G. Pahlavan, R. Pieruschka, N. Pade and B. Stechmann, "Recommendations towards cooperation between African and European research infrastructures," *Zenodo*, p. <https://zenodo.org/record/4475595>, 2021.
- [2] L. Vincenz-Donnelly, S. Fahrner, G. Pahlavan, P. Garcia, R. Pieruschka, C. Alén Amaro, B. Stechmann, A. Buschiazio, I. Figueroa and M. Kim, "Recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European research infrastructures," *Zenodo*, p. <https://zenodo.org/record/4544374>, 2021.
- [3] L. Vincenz-Donnelly, S. Fahrner, G. Pahlavan, R. Pieruschka, B. Stechmann, A. Canario and M. Kim, "Recommendations towards cooperation between Australian and European research infrastructures," *Zenodo*, p. <https://zenodo.org/record/4546173>, 2021.
- [4] RI-VIS, "Collaboration Resources," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/resources>.
- [5] RI-VIS, "Research Infrastructure Communicators Slack Workspace," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/slack>.
- [6] ICRI, "ICRI 2021 Proceedings Report," pp. <http://icri2021.ca/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/ICRI-2021-Proceedings-Report.pdf>, 2021.
- [7] *Towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures (EU-LAC ResInfra)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871140>, 2019.
- [8] Life Science RIs, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>.
- [9] *ERIC Forum Implementation project (ERIC Forum)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/823798>, 2019.
- [10] ENVRI Community, "Board of European environmental research infrastructures (BEERi)," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://envri.eu/beer/>.
- [11] ENVRI Community, "About," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://envri.eu/about/>.
- [12] *Research Infrastructures Training Programme (RItrain)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/654156>, 2015.
- [13] *Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services (CatRIS)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824173>, 2019.
- [14] *European Network of Research Infrastructures & Industry for Collaboration (ENRIITC)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871112>, 2020.